

Role of Social Media in Consumer Purchasing Behaviour of FMCG Products in Delhi

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Abstract: Social media is usually use for making awareness and marketing products. It isn't always smooth to evaluate how much internet marketing attracts the consumers. The aim of this paper is to find out how much marketing and marketing on social media bring impact at the customer's shopping behaviour regarding selected FMCGs. A social media that has been taken on this study (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, Youtube, OLX, and others) with the assist of fivepoint Likert scale with cross sectional information's even hundred questionnaire had been circulated in Delhi as a whole, as an sample, and got 150 complete questionnaires after field overview by respondents. With the help of logistic regression version which have one dependent and different independent variables, a conceptual system became created. Data became tested by the usage of exclusive statistical strategies like such as descriptive statistic, chi-square, and regression with the assist of SPSS software. Findings of the studies are vigorous due to the fact the results display that online advertising have massive affects on consumers' shopping for decisions and their perception.

Key Words: Social Media, Fast-Moving Consumer Goods, Buying Decision, Customer, Attitude

I. Introduction

Social Media is a famous mode for social communication. The 21st century uses social media platforms in their everyday life. In the demanding and competition life, individuals don't have time to get the products or to purchase the products by going to market. Social media assists with overcoming this issue. Online media gives a stage to expand brand awareness, build up the brand's recommendation, and inform the customers regarding the brand, and make a discourse with expected customers. SMM and agencies have a rising activity in marketing, which has large implications for the way customers and businesses execute. In SMM, customers grant on-line input/remarks about objects or products, and these input/remarks is seen to distinctive specialists, such as distinctive consumers, channel accomplices, contenders, and monetary backers. The literature survey showed that social media appear to be influential at the various phases of the purchaser's buying decisions. The sites like Facebook, WhatsApp, LinkedIn, Twitter, Youtube, and so forth

draw more than 5 million customers consistently. Having a presence on these sites/channels is a must for all advertising agencies/organizations.

II. Review of Literature

Kotler and Armstrong (2001) suggested that customer decision refers to the buying decision of households and people who buy the product and personal use of the product. Customers around the world vary according to various factors such as education, training, and age. They affect how you add products and services. This decision subsequently had an impact on products and management practices in certain customer markets. There are many factors that affect consumers' psychological, personal, social and cultural decisions.

OTX DEI Global Survey (2008) suggested in study, they analyzed the influence of online media on customer buying behavior and conduct a research on the US people. The results showed that buyers use online media on the Internet with rich data. Resources In addition, it shows that by-products and business efforts of the network, especially when provided by personal online agents, are undoubtedly more important to customer behavior than clear promotional instructions or guidelines. Undoubtedly, 66% of customers share the information they receive with others, and more than half of customers believe they need this data for activities. The use of the Internet as an optimistic attempt to disseminate data has a greater impact on consumer behavior.

Sukato and Elsey (2009) investigated the miracle of men buying healthy skin products in Thailand. To achieve the purpose of the research, Fishbein and Eisen hypothesized the reason why the activity model was blocked as a system hypothesis, and changed it by including self-confidence or self-esteem. Respect the research results confirm that when male consumers in Bangkok buy healthy skin products, psychological self-portraits, attitudes, standardization affect and influence purchase goals and purchase behaviors. In this sense, the revised hypothesis of legitimate activities is applicable to surrounding purchases of beauty products in Thailand Educate male consumers at the same time.

Hensel and Dayes (2010) found that in order to influence consumer performance, advertisers need to take a positive attitude towards the use of social media. Any social network system has related benefits, losses and difficulties, and these problems must be solved before any specific network system is created. The method of living in social net works has been implemented. Organizations should encourage the development of online information sources and social media conversations. In addition, social media methods should be used to track the company's online status and ensure that consumers do not damage brand equity.

Leslie Martinka (2012) the research examines how social media communities influence customer behavior and help shape social standards and belief systems. This study was conducted with a group of people from Twitter and Facebook who influenced consumers' attitudes towards shopping on internet. The motive of this survey is to getting feedback about the use of social net working sites on the Internet. The out comes how that daily Internet networks control the goods consumers buy online. Research has found that Facebook has an impact on consumers' online shopping experience. The decision and the crowd on Twitter were not affected. This means that Facebook, not Twitter, has a huge impact on buyers who buy the brand.

Rasool, Muhammad Sajid (2012) Discover the influence of advertising on consumer decision-making in Lahore, and plan to understand people's perceptions and perceptions about toothpaste brands in fast-moving consumer products. He also suggested changing consumer choices through wages so that men prefer advertising to women. Advertising can change the way consumers buy products, but it will not affect expensive products and duplication. Facilitate product purchase decisions.

Sonkusare Geeta (2013) The study summarized the impact of TV advertising on female consumer buying behavior, citing the fast-moving consumer goods industry in Chandrapur. He found that most consumers are satisfied with advertisements for fast-moving consumer products. A TV show about their purchase behavior for the largest number of fast-moving consumer goods products. Through TV advertising, women are attracted by the nature of the promotion. Therefore, TV advertising is bound to have a significant impact on consumers' buying behavior. Ladies buyers gather more data about fast-moving consumer goods from advertising and make proper buying from the market. Factors such as innovation, social, financial, political and demographic factors have a greater impact on consume rbehavior, but female consumers are increasingly similar to the impact of personal and social factors.

Balakrishnan (2014) this research paper found the impact of online media on product picture and purchasing assessment of a more youthful age group. 200 surveys were conveyed to college scholar of in Malaysia's colleges. The answer rate was seventy five percent. Three assumption and two recommendations were check utilizing multivariate research and average or normality. The result showed that the social trades, web systems, electronic verbal and on-line exposure are fruitful in advancing the brand picture and purchasing goal of buyers through online life stages. These findings tell the manager to reach at the younger age consumers. Lastly this study proved that social media is the best tool or instrument for increasing sales. This analysis gives data to international sellers in applying internet based life exercises to advertise their product.

S. Sathiyaraj (2015) analyzed that appreciative the discernments in the direction of online purchasing for food in Chennai. It reasoned that, socioeconomics profiles like age, sexual orientation doesn't have any situation to impact on consumer loyalty. Customer favored conventional strategy for online shopping for food than on the web or internet. But, some online respondents expect a few advantages like easy to use sites, simple to arrange, variety, discount offers, less devouring time and keep away from hold up in line and so forth which helps for online shopping for food.

Awan and Abdul Ghafoor (2016) investigate how much marketing brings an impact on the consumer purchasing decisions concerning fast-moving buyer products. With the assistance of Kirkpatrick model that contains five autonomous factors, with one dependent a conceptual system was created. The research signifies that the proof showed that advertisements have more impact on customers' buying decisions.

III. Objective of the Research

To study the increasing trend and role of online/social media on consumer purchasing behaviour with reference to selected fast moving consumer goods

Hypothesis H0: There is no significant role and impact of social media on consumer's buying decision with reference to FMCG.

IV. Research Methodology

This research was attempted to know the purchasing attitude of the customers towards online media advertising destinations and to know the elements which impact the purchasing attitude/behaviour towards selected skincare, hair care, and fragrances products on social media sites and how these elements play a significant part in purchasing behaviour. The information needed for the research was gathered from the sample respondents of Delhi by an online questionnaire. The absolute sample of 150 was selected which impacted the buyer purchasing behaviour. The significant data was gathered from primary as well as secondary data were gathered from different books, records, yearly reports, different distributions, and sites. The information collected has been prepared and arranged by utilizing SPSS programming and to some

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degree physically. Basic statistical tools average method and binary logistics analysis have been utilized to examine the information.

V.1 Data Analysis and Results

Table 1
General Background Information

PARTICULAR	CLASSIFICATION	PERCENTAGE
Gender	Male	55.4
	Female	44.6
Respondent's Age	Less than 25 Years	23.1
	25-35 Years	32.7
	35-45 Years	33.3
	Above 45 Years	10.9
Marital Status	Married	57.0
	Un-Married	43.0
Education of the Respondents	Up to 12th	14.8
	Graduate	16.2
	Post Graduate	48.6
	Others (Diploma etc)	20.4
Occupation of the Respondents	Student	30.7
	Businessman	14.5
	Govt. Employee	28.0
	Professional	17.8
	Others	19.0
Monthly Income	Less than 25,000 (Lower income group)	35.0
	25,000-50,000 (middle income group)	17.9
	50,000-75,000 (middle upper income group)	20.6
	More than 75,000 (upper income group)	26.5
Expenditure on selected FMCG Products (weekly)	Less than 3,000	50.6
	3,000-6,000	24.7
	6,000-8,000	11.2
	More than 8,000	13.5

Source: Data 2020

Interpretation: Table 1 demonstrate the sex of the peoples who participated in the study, 55.4% were male and 44.6% were female, which indicates that most of the respondents in the research are male respondents. The table shows that the youngest age group under 25 accounted for 23.1%, 32.7% of the 25 to 35 age group, 33.3% of the 35 to 45 age group, and 10.9% of the above 45-year-old. The marital status of the interviewee shows 57% are married and 43% are single. The education level of the respondents shows that they studied before high school, accounting for 14.8% of the sample, studying up to graduation, which is 16.2% of the sample, and studying up to post graduation, accounting for 48.6% of the total sample. Other courses such as diplomas, etc. accounted for 20.4% of the total sample, indicating that the sample of interviewees in this study is well-educated. The outcomes confirmed that within side the overall sample, 30.7% students, and the businessmen 14.5%, followed by other 19%, belong to other categories of government servants, accounting for 28%, and professionals 17.8%. 35% of the peoples who was

participated in the study have an income level of less than 25,000, that is, 17.9% of the respondents belong to the group with an average income between 25,000 and 50,000, and about 20.6% of the respondents have an income between 50,000 and 75,000. As a high-income group, 26.5% of respondents belong to more than 75,000 categories. The table shows that in the group of less than 3,000 people, 50.6% of the respondents are at the monthly spending level of consumer goods, and most of the respondents said this. Although 24.7% of participated peoples in study are in the category of 3,000 to 6,000, about 11.2% of participated peoples in study spend between 6,000 to 8,000 per month, and 13.5% of respondents fall into more than 8,000 categories.

V.2 Pre-purchase attitude with gender wise towards consumption of FMCG product

Table 2
Binary Logistic Analysis

Independent Variables	B	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Prejudgement	-.289	1.032	.317	.732
Convenient	-.019	.012	.904	.961
Consistent	.115	.148	.681	1.101
Perception change	.034	.012	.872	1.035
Constant	.333	.947	.318	1.419
-2 log likelihood	655.58			
Dependent variable = if it is 1, for male and if it 0, for female				

Source: Data 2020

Interpretation: Table 2 shows that compared with women, men have negative reactions due to the prejudice and convenience of consumer products. On the other hand, men are 1.101 times more likely to find increasingly popular products than women. Compared with women, their views on consumer products always change 1.035 times. However, not all variables are statistically significant.

V.3Pre-purchase attitude in education wise towards Consumption of FMCG product

Table 3
Binary Logistic Analysis

Independent Variables	B	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Prejudgement	1.187	6.053	.004	3.211
Convenient	-.371	1.26	.250	.673
Consistent	.534	2.1574	.130	1.623
Perception change	-1.010	9.474	.002	.320
Constant	-1.815	13.361	.000	.137
-2 log likelihood	412.96			
Dependent variable = if it is 1, for 12th student and if it is 0, for above 12th student				

Source: Data 2020

Interpretation: Table 3 shows that, compared with 12th students, 12th class students are 3.211 times more likely to be biased and 1.623 times more likely to find an agreed option for pre-purchasing FMCG products,

but this match is not statistically significant. On the other hand, changes in convenience and perception show negative reactions to mass consumer products.

V.4 Pre-purchase attitude with occupation towards Consumption of FMCG product

Table 4
Binary Logistic Analysis

Independent Variables	B	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Prejudgement	.950	7.170	.017	2.513
Convenient	-.232	.706	.387	.775
Consistent	.417	2.116	.137	1.433
Perception change	-.877	8.082	.003	.402
Constant	-1.023	6.669	.008	.346
-2 log likelihood	579.88			
Dependent variable = if it is 1, for student and if it is 0, for other occupation like businessman, govt. employee, professionals and others				

Source: Data 2020

Interpretation: Table 4 shows that compared with other professions such as business people, civil servants, and others, students' preference for consumer goods is always 2.513 times higher; this is statistically significant at the 1% significance level. In addition, these students always have 1.433 times more consumer goods at their disposal than other occupations. On the other hand, changes in convenience and concepts reflect negative reactions to mass consumer products.

V.5 Pre-purchase attitude with income of respondents towards consumption of FMCG product

Table 5
'Binary Logistic Analysis

Independent Variables	B	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Prejudgement	.444	2.001	.146	1.564
Convenient	.021	.002	.902	1.022
Consistent	-.078	.110	.741	.906
Perception change	.204	.454	.486	1.138
Constant	-1.013	8.287	.014	.318
-2 log likelihood	618.55			
Dependent variable = if it is 1, for person whose income below Rs. 25000 and if it is 0, for more than Rs. 25000				

Source: Data 2020

Interpretation: According to table 5 above, people with an income of more than 25,000 rupees are always 1.564 times more likely to be comfortable, 1.022 times more likely to feel comfortable, and those with an income of less than 25,000 rupees are always 1.238 times more likely Times. Change your perception of consumer products by consistently showing negative reactions. However, not all variables are statistically significant.

V.5 Factors in advertisement influence buying decision to purchase the FMCG products on social media site/channel

Table 6 below shows how promotions affect consumers' purchasing decisions. Respondents gave their responses on a scale of one to five, in which one meant I strongly agree, two meant I agree, three meant neutral, four meant disagree, and five meant strongly disagree. The mean value, the nearer to 1, the higher the consistency.

Table 6
Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean/ Average	Std. Deviation
Ordered product on social media reaches on time	2.41	1.16
Taken decision on social media is easy	2.52	1.27
Good quality products available on social media	2.73	1.18
Products on social media has satisfactory prices	2.72	1.24
Company meets the promises which is on social media for products	2.83	1.17
Delivery person's attitude influence buying decision	2.71	1.25
Share the comments to others after purchasing products on social media	2.72	1.16
Social media build a good relation with other	2.53	1.14
Give feedback to other after buying the products	2.54	1.12
Information of products has a higher reliability on social media than mass media	2.51	1.20

Source: Data 2020

Figure.1

Influencing Factor for consumer behavior on FMCG (in Percentage)

Source: Data 2020

Interpretation: The results show that the average value of "social media order arrives on time for FMCG" is 2.41, the Std. Dev. is 1.16, and the "social media make decision making"-the average value is 2.52, the Std.

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Dev. is 1.27, and the "FMCG social product" media, The average value of "good quality" is 2.73, the Std. Dev. is 1.18, and the average value of "satisfaction with the price of fast moving consumer goods purchased on social media" is 2.72 and the Std. Dev. of 1.24, the average value of "company keeps promises in social media advertising" is 2.83, the Std. Dev. is 1.17, the average value of "dealer buying behavior" is 2.71, and the Std. Dev. is 1.25, Buy fast moving consumer goods through social media Comments/comments/posts with family or friends after the brand "on average the Std. Dev. of 2.72 and 1.16, "Social media provides customers with an effective and influential platform for customers to build relationships with others and the company", with an average of 2.53 and a Std. Dev. of 1.14: "Share your thoughts at any time afterwards Buying products on social media has an "average 2.54 and a Std. Dev. of 1.12". Brand information on social media is more reliable than a media website because the information it cannot control is on average 2.51 and has a Std. Dev. is 1.20.

VIII. Chi Square test on Social Media and Buying Decision

To verify the hypothesis that 'There is no significant influence of social media advertising on consumer's shopping for selection with regards to FMCG.' The chi square test was used.

Table 7

Social Media sites influencing to buy the FMCG Products

Time spent on SMM in week	Social Media Sites trigger to Purchase FMCG Products					Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
Less than 4 hours	12.5	33.2	19.7	19.7	13.0	100
4-8 hours	19.6	39.2	16.9	16.0	9.4	100
8-12 hours	24.1	41.2	24.0	11.6	0.0	100
12-16 hours	22.1	55.4	11.3	5.3	7.0	100
More than 16 hours	26.0	47.5	14.0	11.5	0.0	100
All	18.8	40.1	18.2	14.7	8.3	100

Source: Data 2020

Figure 2

Social Media influencing buying decision of FMCG Products

Table 8
Chi-square Test

Statistics	Value	df	p-value
Chi-Square Tests	36.543	16	.002

Interpretation: The chi-square test result shows the test statistics and their meanings. In the table 8 above the chi-square result is 36.543, while df is shown as sixteen, and the p-value is 0.002, so that is the outcomes. Table 8 above shows that since the p-value of the chi-square test is less than 0.05, the null hypotheses should be rejected and conclusions that all social media sites induce or influence respondents to produce fast-moving consumer products, and indicate that social network sites affect consumers' purchasing decisions, and some consumers use them very frequently. The results show in percentage in table 7 above confirm that respondents (40.1%) agree to Spend greater than sixteen hours on SM sites, and strongly agree (54%) spend 12 to 16 hours on social media each week so prove that these sites are very common.

IX. Limitation of the Study

1. Buyer behavior is affected by many factors such as education, occupation, salary, gender, and age.
2. There are different types of informal communication platforms, such as Twitter, WhatsApp, YouTube, Facebook, and many other platforms that influence buyer behavior.
3. The information/data collected in this study is as of 2020 and in Delhi on a limited consumer base.

X. Conclusion

The results of the study concluded that a study examined the influence of various factors on the purchase behavior of consumers of skin, hair, and perfume products; with higher education and younger age, respondents were more likely to use the product. After checking the initial consensus information on social media and changing their views on purchasing commodities, low-income male respondents were the most affected by viewing comments on social media. Although both men and women with the lowest incomes are affected by social media website advertisements, social media factors can change buyers' attitudes towards choosing relatives, commenting on family members, predicting experience, product/product information, and brand reputation. Celebrities or celebrities, brand pricing information, discounts, and plans. Research shows that the decisions made by relatives, and friends when purchasing consumer goods on social networks have a greater impact on respondents' decisions. Compared with female respondents, male students changed their initial purchasing decision. The existence of social media, that is, the relationship between online media and shoppers' purchasing decisions, shows that social media will affect customers' attitudes towards advertising, brand prospects, and purchase expectations. The study also shows that social media marketing websites have a greater influence on the purchasing decisions of low-income group of men respondents.

Bibliography

- Awan and Abdul Ghafoor (2016)** Effects of Advertisement on Consumer's Buying Behaviour with References to FMCGs in Southern Punjab-Pakistan, *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research*, 19, pg. 22-30
- Balakrishnan (2014)** The Impact of Social Media Marketing Medium Toward Purchase Intention and Brand Loyalty Among Generation Y, Available online at www.sciencedirect.com, *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 148 (2014) pg.177-185
- Hensel, K., & Deis M. H. (2010)** Using Social Media to Increase Advertising and Improve Marketing, *Entrepreneurial Executive*, 15, pg. 87-97

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Leslie and Martinka (2012) "How Social Media Communities Impact Consumer Behavior" ,Master of Arts dissertation, Gonzaga University

Rasool, Muhammad Sajid (2012) Impact of advertisement on consumer behavior of FMCG in Lahore city, Academic Research International, 2(3), pg.571-574

S. Sathiyaraj (2015) 'Consumer perception towards online grocery stores, Chennai', 'Zenith International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research', ISSN 2231-5780, Vol 5(6), pg.24- 33

Sonkusare, Geeta (2013) Impact of television advertising on buying behavior of women consumers' (With special reference to FMCG Products) Chandrapur city. International Journal of Business and Management Invention 2(3) pg.31-38

Sukato, N., and Elsey, B. (2009) "A model of male consumer behaviour in buying skin care products in Thailand", ABAC Journal, Vol. 29, No. 1, pg.39-52

TEI Worldwide OTX Research (2008) "The Impact of Social Media on Purchasing Behavior," USA